

Synthesis, reactions and characterization of some mixed ligand (phenoxo-alkoxo- and acetylacetonato-) complexes of cobalt(II) derived from Schiff bases^ψ

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Abstract : Some novel complexes of cobalt(II) of the type, $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(sb)}\}_2]$ (1) and (2) and $\text{Co}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(sb)}\}_2$ (3) and (4) [where sb = Schiff base {salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (smabH) for (1 and 3) and salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (sapH) for (2 and 4)}, η^2 = number of connectivity sites involved in bonding metal] have been synthesized by the simple metathetic reactions of anhydrous cobalt(II) chloride with sodium salt of corresponding Schiff bases in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio (in C_6H_6 -THF mixture). The complexes (1) and (2) have been treated with various sodium salts of tetraalkoxyaluminate, acetylacetonate and phenolate to produce new mixed ligand complexes of the type $[(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_2\}_2\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(sb)}\}]$ (1a and 2a) and $[(\mu\text{-OEt})_2\{\text{Al}(\text{OEt})_2\}_2\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(sb)}\}]$ (1b and 2b) : $[\eta^2\text{-(acac)}_2\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(sb)}\}]$ (1c₁ and 1c₂) and $[(\mu\text{-OAr})_2\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(sb)}\}]$ for (1d₁ and 1d₃), [where (acac) = $(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)$ for (1c₁), (acac) = $(\text{CF}_3\text{COCHCOCF}_3)$ for (1c₂), (acac) = $(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCF}_3)$ for (1c₃); Ar = 2,6-Me₂C₆H₃ (for 1d₁); Ar = 3,5-Me₂C₆H₃ (for 1d₂) and Ar = *p*-ClC₆H₄ (for 1d₃). All these derivatives have been characterized by elemental analysis, spectral (IR, UV-visible) and magnetic susceptibility measurements.

Keywords : Cobalt(II), Schiff bases, phenols, alkoxides.

During recent years¹, we have been interested to prepare hydrocarbon soluble mixed ligand complexes containing salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (smabH), salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (sapH) as well as (*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-benzoxazole (Hpbbox) and (*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-benzimidazole (Hpbz) organic moieties.

However, some novel heterometallic complexes of the later '3d' transition metals containing alkoxo-, aryloxo- and acetylacetonato-moieties have received only scant attention². Keeping above in view, it is of great interest to explore the chemistry, and bonding characteristics to throw light towards coordination behaviour and structural aspects of various mixed ligand Schiff base complexes of transition metals.

Therefore, we report herein the synthesis (1-4) and chemical reactivity of cobalt(II) complexes, $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(smab)}\}_2]$ 1 and $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(sap)}\}_2]$ 2, $[\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(smab)}\}_2]$ 3, $[\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(sap)}\}_2]$ 4, as well as their structural characterization by spectroscopic and magnetic studies.

Results and discussion

Synthesis : New complexes of cobalt(II) containing Schiff base have been prepared by the reactions of anhydrous cobalt(II) chloride with sodium salts of salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene Na(smab) and salicylidene-2-aminopyridine Na(sap) in different molar ratios, afforded complexes of the type $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(smab)}\}_2]$ 1, $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(sap)}\}_2]$ 2, $[\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(smab)}\}_2]$ 3 and $[\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-(sap)}\}_2]$ 4 which can be illustrated by the following chemical equations :

(where sb = smabH for 1 and 3; sb = sapH for 2 and 4)

^ψDedicated to (late) Professor R. C. Mehrotra - Father of Metal Alkoxide Chemistry on his 85th birthday.

The freshly prepared complexes are coloured solid and soluble in common organic solvents. The solubility of products (1) and (2) decreases after few days. However, these are highly soluble in THF, DMSO, DMF and CHCl₃, and purified by recrystallization in C₆H₆-THF mixture. Attempts have been made to purify these derivatives by volatilization under reduced pressure (at very high temperature) but we could not succeed.

The chemical reactivity of monochloro cobalt(II) complexes (1) and (2) with sodium tetraalkoxyaluminate,* such as [Na{Al(OPrⁱ)₄}] and [Na{Al(OEt)}₄] produced new alkoxo-bridged bimetallic complexes of the types [η²-(sb)Co{Al(OPrⁱ)}] (1a and 2a) and [η²-(sb)Co{Al(OEt)}] (1b and 2b), which can be shown by the following chemical equations :

When monochloro complex [(smb)Co(Cl)] (1) has been treated with sodium salt of β-diketone produced new β-diketonate derivatives of cobalt(II) :

{where (acac) = CH₃COCHCOCH₃ for (1c₁), (acac) = CF₃COCHCOCF₃ for (1c₂) and (acac) =

CH₃COCHCOCF₃ for (1c₃)}.

Further, complex (1) has been treated with sodium salts of various phenoxide, to produce phenoxo-bridge complexes of the type [(η²-smab)Co₂(μ-OAr)₂] (1d₁-1d₃) which can be illustrated by the following chemical equation :

{where Ar = 2,6-Me₂-C₆H₃ (1d₁), 3,5-Me₂-C₆H₃ (1d₂) and *p*-Cl-C₆H₄ (1d₃)}.

All these above derivatives have found to be coloured solid and are soluble in common organic solvents, have been purified by recrystallization in C₆H₆/*n*-hexane mixture.

It is important to mention that alkoxo-bridged complexes (1a, 1b, 2a and 2b) undergo decomposition on heating even under reduced pressure. Only a representative decomposition reaction has been given below :

Magnetic studies :

The magnetic moment values (at room temperature) of the synthesized Schiff base complexes of cobalt(II) are observed in the range 4.00–4.85 B.M. (Table 1). The alkoxo-bridge complexes of cobalt(II) (1a, 1b) exhibit 4.70–4.92 B.M., which corresponds to the reported³ value 4.80–5.20 B.M. confirming high spin octahedral com-

Table 1. Electronic (UV-visible) spectral and magnetic data of various complex of cobalt(II) containing Schiff base

Sl. no.	Compds.	Transitions (cm ⁻¹) ⁴ T _{1g} (F) $\xrightarrow{\nu_3}$ ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	CT Bands [ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹)]	μ _{eff} (B.M.) (Room temp.)
1.	[(μ-Cl) ₂ Co ₂ (η ² -smab) ₂] 1	1800, 20500 (sh)	27352 31645, 32467, 33333	4.20
2.	[(μ-Cl) ₂ Co ₂ (η ² -sap) ₂] 2	1800, 20000 (sh)	26178 34965	4.00
3.	[Co(η ² -smab) ₂] 3	17900, 21000	28860 31104, 34188	4.85
4.	[Co(η ² -sap) ₂] 4	18200, 20500	27384 32808	4.80
5.	[(η ² -(acac)Co(η ² -smab) ₂] 1c ₁	17800, 21000	28985 32467	4.82
6.	[(η ² -smab)Co(μ-OAr) ₂] 1d ₁	18000, 20800	25615 31312	4.10
7.	[(η ² -smab)Co(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ {Al(OPr ⁱ) ₂ }] 1a	18000, 21000	28943 31152, 34246	4.92
8.	[(η ² -sap)Co(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ {Al(OPr ⁱ) ₂ }] 1b	18000, 20000	27077 31841	-
9.	[(η ² -smab)Co(OEt) ₂ {Al(OEt) ₂ }] 2b	18700, 20900	26300 30300	4.70

For smabH, C.T. Band = 28400 cm⁻¹; for sapH, C.T. Band = 27600 cm⁻¹.

plexes of cobalt(II). The phenoxo-bridged complexes of cobalt(II) exhibit lower 4.10 B.M. value in comparison to complexes of cobalt(II) containing β -diketonate 4.82 B.M. The monochloro cobalt(II) complexes also exhibit lower value 4.00–4.20 B.M. in comparison to β -diketonate-cobalt(II) complexes. This may be possible due to dimerisation of molecule in solid state through the formation of chlorine-bridged or phenoxo-bridged between two cobalt(II) center. However, β -diketonate ligand behave as bidentate ligand, hence there is no possibility for the dimerisation and therefore the observed magnetic moment value for the complexes containing both these moieties (β -diketonate and Schiff base) are comparatively higher. It may be therefore concluded that the geometry around cobalt(II) is octahedral (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Proposed structure for $[(\mu\text{-OPr})_2\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr})_2\}\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-smab}\}]$ (1a).

Electronic spectra :

The UV-visible spectra of cobalt(II) complexes syn-

thesized during the present course of investigations were measured in THF or DMSO. All these derivatives showed an unsymmetric band in the region 18000 cm^{-1} (Table 1), which can be assigned⁴ as ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \xrightarrow{V_3} {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, characteristic for distorted octahedral geometry (Scheme 2). The Schiff base complexes showed charge transfer band in the UV region at $\sim 28145 \pm 80\text{ cm}^{-1}$, this may be attributable to the charge transfer transition. In addition to this band, two intense bands at around $32000 \pm 60\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have also been observed and may be assigned to intra ligand charge transfer transition.

Scheme 2. Proposed structure for $[(\mu\text{-X})_2\text{Co}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(sb)}\}]$ [where sb = sap or smab; Y = N, for sap and Y = C-CH₃ for smab and X = Cl or Ar (Ar = 2,6-Me₂-C₆H₃ (1d₁), 3,5-Me₂-C₆H₃ (1d₂), *p*-Cl-C₆H₄ (1d₃)).

IR spectra :

The important IR frequencies for the newly synthesized mixed ligand complexes are given in Table 2. The

Table 2. Characteristic IR absorption frequencies (cm^{-1}) of various complexes of cobalt(II) containing Schiff base

Sl. no.	Complexes	$\nu_{\text{Co-Cl}}$	$\nu_{\text{Co-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{Co-O}}$	$\nu_{(\text{C-O})\text{M}}$ Phenolic	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{(\text{C-O})\text{Co}}$ Alkoxy	$\nu_{(\text{Al-O})}$	$\nu_{\text{C-C}}$	$\nu_{\text{O=O}}$
1.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}_2(\eta^2\text{-smab})_2]$ 1	300, 307, 318	445, 411	515	1283	1620	-	-	-	-
2.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}_2(\eta^2\text{-sap})_2]$ 2	293, 302, 314, 329	440	535	1278	1625	-	-	-	-
3.	$[\text{Co}(\eta^2\text{-smab})_2]$ 3	-	425	520	1280	1622	-	-	-	-
4.	$[\text{Co}(\eta^2\text{-sap})_2]$ 4	-	430	489, 531	1282	1625	-	-	-	-
5.	$[(\eta^2\text{-smab})\text{Co}(\mu\text{-OPr})_2\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr})_2\}]$ 1a	-	430	518	1280	1615	1150 ^t , 960 ^b	610	-	-
6.	$[(\eta^2\text{-smab})\text{Co}(\mu\text{-OEt})_2\{\text{Al}(\text{OEt})_2\}]$ 1b	-	415, 381	507	1285	1617	1140 ^t , 950 ^b	600	-	-
7.	$[(\eta^2\text{-sap})\text{Co}(\mu\text{-OPr})_2\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr})_2\}]$ 2a	-	421	485	1276	1623	1160 ^t , 960 ^b	570	-	-
8.	$[(\eta^2\text{-sap})\text{Co}(\mu\text{-OEt})_2\{\text{Al}(\text{OEt})_2\}]$ 2b	-	418	480	1282	1619	1150 ^t , 955 ^b	600	-	-
9.	$[(\eta^2\text{-acac})\text{Co}(\eta^2\text{-smab})_2]$ 1c ₁	-	430	500	1276	1621	-	-	1540	1610
10.	$[(\eta^2\text{-acac})\text{Co}(\eta^2\text{-smab})_2]$ 1c ₂	-	435, 442	530	1281	1620	-	-	1535	1615
11.	$[(\eta^2\text{-acac})\text{Co}(\eta^2\text{-smab})_2]$ 1c ₃	-	416	517	1275	1608	-	-	1590	1610
12.	$[(\eta^2\text{-smab})\text{Co}(\mu\text{-OAr})_2]$ 1d ₁	-	422	491, 502	1292	1617	-	-	-	-
13.	$[(\eta^2\text{-smab})\text{Co}(\mu\text{-OAr})_2]$ 1d ₂	-	408, 429	487	1288	1615	-	-	-	-
14.	$[(\eta^2\text{-smab})\text{Co}(\mu\text{-OAr})_2]$ 1d ₃	-	430	495	1285	1610	-	-	-	-

t = terminal alkoxy, *b* = bridging alkoxy.

For smabH, ν_{CH} = 3450 cm^{-1} ; for sapH, ν_{OH} = 3407 cm^{-1} , $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ = 1628 cm^{-1} , ν_{pyridine} = 3129 cm^{-1} .

presence of Schiff base moiety indicated by the appearance of absorption band at 1630 and 1628 cm^{-1} is the characteristic of $\text{C}=\text{N}$. In the complexes it gets shifted to lower frequency region suggesting participation of azomethine group in the complexation⁵. The phenolic ($\text{C}-\text{O}$) stretching frequencies were observed at 1275–1260 cm^{-1} in Schiff bases and phenoxide. These bands have appeared in the range 1289–1277 cm^{-1} in complexes are characteristic for bond formation between metal and phenolic oxygen^{5,6}. Pyridynyl group⁷ of *sapH* showed absorption bands at 3129 cm^{-1} . The chloro complexes (**1** and **2**) showed characteristic IR bands due to $\nu_{\text{Co}-\text{Cl}}$ ⁸ frequencies at 300(s), 307(s) and 318(m) in complex (**1**) and 293(s), 302(s) and 314(s) in complex (**2**). Presence of absorption bands in β -diketonate cobalt(II) derivatives (**1c₁**–**1c₃**) around 1610 cm^{-1} and 1540 cm^{-1} are due to $\nu_{\text{Co}=\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ bands, respectively⁵. Phenoxo-bridged⁹ derivatives (**1d₁**–**1d₃**) $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}(\text{phenolic})}$ band shifted to the higher frequency region by ~ 11 –20 cm^{-1} , thereby showing coordination between R–O and cobalt as well as an evidence for the formation of phenolic oxygen bridge¹⁰. In alkoxy bridged derivatives (**1a**, **1b**, **2a**, **2b**), aluminium isopropoxide or ethoxide exhibits characteristic frequencies due to $\nu_{(\text{C}-\text{O})\text{M}}$ ¹¹ for metal-alkoxy group in the range 1170–930 cm^{-1} . Band in the range 610–540 cm^{-1} has been assigned for $\nu_{\text{Al}-\text{O}}$.

Infrared spectra of all the cobalt(II) complexes showed characteristic IR frequencies in the region 510 ± 15 and $415 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which have been assigned for $\nu_{\text{Co}-\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Co}-\text{N}}$, respectively.

On the basis of spectral (IR and UV-visible) and magnetic studies, tentative structures for these complexes may be proposed (Schemes 1–3).

Scheme 3. Proposed structure for $[(\eta^2\text{-acac})\text{Co}\{\eta^2\text{-smab}\}]$ (**1c₁**–**1c₃**) [where, $\text{R} = \text{R}' = \text{CH}_3$ (for **1c₁**), $\text{R} = \text{R}' = \text{CF}_3$ (for **1c₂**) and $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$ and $\text{R}' = \text{CF}_3$ (for **1c₃**)]

Experimental

All experiments were carried out in moisture free atmosphere. The solvents were dried by standard literature

procedures. The anhydrous CoCl_2 was prepared as reported earlier². Aluminium isopropoxide and aluminium ethoxide were prepared and analysed by literature method¹¹. Cobalt was determined as mixed oxide, aluminium was determined as oxinate $[\text{Al}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_3]$. Isopropyl and ethyl alcohol were determined by oxidimetric method¹². Chloride was estimated by Volhard's method. Molecular heights were determined cryoscopically in freezing benzene by Beckmann thermometer. IR (4000–200 cm^{-1}) and electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer grating and Pay-Unicam model 557/SP8-100 spectrophotometer, respectively. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as standard.

Preparation of Schiff bases :

The Schiff bases, salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (*smabH*)¹³ and salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (*sapH*)¹⁴ have been prepared by previously established methods.

Preparation of monochloro complexes of cobalt(II) of the type $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}_2(\eta^2\text{-smab})_2]$ **1** and $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}_2(\eta^2\text{-sap})_2]$ **2** :

To a stirred hot suspension of anhydrous CoCl_2 (0.36 g, 2.80 mmol) in THF ($\sim 30 \text{ cm}^3$) was added a freshly prepared $\text{Na}(\text{smab})$ (0.65 g, 2.80 mmol) [prepared by adding *smabH* (0.62 g, 2.80 mmol)] dissolved in benzene ($\sim 25 \text{ cm}^3$) to a solution of isopropanol ($\sim 5 \text{ cm}^3$) containing sodium metal (0.064 g, 2.80 mmol) in 1 : 1 stoichiometric ratio. The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for ~ 2 h, during which time, the colour of the solution changed from blue to green. The precipitated NaCl (0.16 g, 2.40 mmol) was removed by filtration. The solvent was stripped off under reduced pressure to afford a green solid which was purified by recrystallisation from THF-benzene mixture to give $[(\text{smab})\text{Co}(\text{Cl})]$ (**1**) (0.80 g, 94%).

Similar method was adopted to prepare derivative $[(\text{sap})\text{Co}(\text{Cl})]$ **2**. The details of these reactions and their analytical data are given in Table 3.

Preparation of $[\text{Co}(\eta^2\text{-smab})_2]$ **3** complex :

To a suspension of anhydrous CoCl_2 (0.24 g, 1.82 mmol) in THF ($\sim 30 \text{ cm}^3$) was added to a freshly prepared $\text{Na}(\text{smab})$ (0.84 g, 3.64 mmol) in 1 : 2 molar ratio [prepared by adding *smabH* (0.77 g, 3.64 mmol)] dissolved in benzene ($\sim 25 \text{ cm}^3$) to a solution of isopropanol ($\sim 5 \text{ cm}^3$) containing sodium metal (0.083 g, 3.64 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed/stirred for ~ 2 h, during which time, the colour of the solution changed from violet to brown. The precipitated NaCl

Table 3. Synthetic and analytical data for the various complexes of cobalt(II) containing Schiff base

Sl. no.	Reactants (g, mmol)	Products (g, % yield)	Physical state	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)		
				Co	Al	OPr ⁱ /OEt
1.	CoCl ₂ + Na(smab) (0.37, 2.80) (0.65, 2.80)	[(smab)CoCl] (1) (0.80, 94)	Green solid	19.5 (19.35)	-	-
2.	CoCl ₂ + Na(sap) (0.39, 3.01) (0.66, 3.00)	[(sap)CoCl] (2) (0.80, 92)	Orange solid	20.45 (20.22)	-	-
3.	CoCl ₂ + Na(smab) (0.24, 1.82) (0.84, 3.64)	[Co(smab) ₂] (3) (0.75, 86)	Brown solid	13.20 (12.82)	-	-
4.	CoCl ₂ + Na(sap) (0.20, 1.55) (0.68, 3.10)	[Co(sap) ₂] (4) (0.55, 78.5)	Black powder solid	13.40 (12.99)	-	-
5.	[(smab)CoCl] + Na{Al(OPr ⁱ) ₄ } (0.73, 2.40) (0.68, 2.40)	[(smab)Co{Al(OPr ⁱ) ₄ }] (1a) (1.05, 82.0)	Green solid	11.20 (11.07)	5.40 (5.06)	11.0 (11.28)
6.	[(smab)CoCl] + Na{Al(OEt) ₄ } (0.39, 1.30) (0.30, 1.30)	[(smab)Co{Al(OEt) ₄ }] (1b) (0.49, 80)	Yellowish green solid	12.60 (12.37)	6.0 (5.66)	12.0 (12.69)
7.	[(sap)CoCl] + Na{Al(OPr ⁱ) ₄ } (0.81, 2.80) (0.80, 2.80)	[(sap)Co{Al(OPr ⁱ) ₄ }] (2a) (1.10, 76)	Dark green solid	11.60 (11.34)	5.28 (5.19)	11.25 (11.56)
8.	[(sap)CoCl] + Na{Al(OEt) ₄ } (0.39, 1.30) (0.30, 1.30)	[(sap)Co{Al(OEt) ₄ }] (2b) (0.54, 78)	Red solid	13.0 (12.71)	6.25 (5.82)	12.20 (12.69)
9.	[(smab)CoCl] + Na(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) (0.73, 2.41) (0.29, 2.41)	[(smab)Co(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃)] (1c ₁) (0.75, 85)	Purple-red solid	16.25 (16.01)	-	-
10.	[(smab)CoCl] + Na(CF ₃ COCHCOCF ₃) (0.48, 1.60) (0.37, 1.61)	[(smab)Co(CF ₃ COCHCOCF ₃)] (1c ₂) (0.62, 82)	Brown solid	12.8 (12.37)	-	-
11.	[(smab)CoCl] + Na(CH ₃ COCHCOCF ₃) (0.45, 1.50) (0.23, 1.50)	[(smab)Co(CH ₃ COCHCOCF ₃)] (1c ₃) (0.49, 80)	Brown solid	15.0 (14.73)	-	-
12.	[(smab)CoCl] + Na(OAr) (0.60, 2.00) (0.28, 2.00)	[(smab)Co(OAr)] (1d ₁) (0.61, 79)	Violet-red solid	15.45 (15.10)	-	-
13.	[(smab)CoCl] + Na(OAr) (0.58, 1.91) (0.27, 1.90)	[(smab)Co(OAr)] (1d ₂) (0.59, 81)	Leaf-brown solid	15.2 (15.10)	-	-
14.	[(smab)CoCl] + Na(OAr) (0.45, 1.51) (0.23, 1.51)	[(smab)Co(OAr)] (1d ₃) (0.45, 78)	Light-violet solid	15.0 (14.86)	-	-

where Ar = 2,6-Me₂-C₆H₃ (1d₁), 3,5-Me₂-C₆H₃ (1d₂), *p*-Cl-C₆H₄ (1d₃).

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

(0.208 g 3.60 mmol) was removed by filtration. After removing the excess of solvent and drying under reduced pressure, brown powdered solid was obtained which was purified by recrystallisation from THF-benzene mixture to give [Co(smab)₂] **3** (0.75 g, 86%). A similar method was adopted to prepare complex [Co(sap)₂] **4**. The details of these reactions and their analytical data are given in Table 3.

Reactions of monochloro cobalt(II) complex, [(μ-Cl)₂Co₂(η²-smab)₂]:

With sodium-tetraisoopropoxyaluminate, Na{Al(OPrⁱ)₄}:

To a benzene (~ 30 cm³) solution of [(smab)Co(Cl)] **1** (0.73 g, 2.40 mmol) a freshly prepared Na[Al(OPrⁱ)₄]

(0.68 g, 2.40 mmol) [prepared by refluxing a solution obtained by addition of Al(OPrⁱ)₃ (0.49 g, 2.40 mmol) in benzene (~ 30 cm³) to a solution of isopropanol (~ 10 cm³) containing sodium metal (0.06 g, 2.40 mmol)] was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed/stirred for ~ 4 h, during which time, the colour of the solution changed from blue to sea green. The reaction mixture was filtered to remove NaCl (0.14 g, 2.40 mmol). The excess of solvent from filtrate was removed by distillation and dried under reduced pressure to afford a dark green coloured solid which was purified by recrystallisation from THF-benzene mixture to give [(smab)Co{Al(OPrⁱ)₄}] (**1a**) (1.05 g, 82.3%).

In a similar manner, derivative [(1b), (2b), (1c₁-1c₃), (1d₂) and (1d₃), (2a)] have been prepared and details are collected in Table 3.

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